

THE UNITY OF TECHNIQUE, TACTICS AND STRATEGY IN TABLE TENNIS.

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Abstract. *This article provides a lot of information on technical, tactical and strategic training of table tennis players in the training process. Recommendations are also presented on the development of technical, tactical and strategic processes in the multi-year training system.*

Keywords: *techniques, tactics, strategies, physical qualities, competitive process, planning and flexibility, theoretical studies, strategic and tactical thinking, volitional qualities.*

ЕДИНСТВО ТЕХНИКИ, ТАКТИКИ И СТРАТЕГИИ В НАСТОЛЬНОМ ТЕННИСЕ.

Аннотация. *В данной статье представлено много информации о технической, тактической и стратегической подготовке игроков в настольный теннис в тренировочном процессе. Также представлены рекомендации по развитию технических, тактических и стратегических процессов в системе многолетней подготовки.*

Ключевые слова: *приемы, тактика, стратегия, физические качества, соревновательный процесс, планирование и гибкость, теоретические занятия, стратегическое и тактическое мышление, волевые качества.*

When the initial mastery of technique, tactics and strategy is completed, the preparatory stage begins, which is characterized by the closest connection of all three structural elements of the competitive process. At this stage, students fully master all advanced types, methods and forms of action, techniques for conducting games, master a set of intellectual, volitional and physical qualities necessary for the implementation of advanced strategic and tactical principles in competitions.

Currently, training is characterized by the most accurate promising direction aimed at using advanced trends in the development of the competitive process in the game, rapid development of the latest models of strategy, tactics and techniques.

It is important to predict the further development of the competitive process, to determine everything that is promising in the game and in training.

In addition to training, they regularly conduct theoretical classes. In these classes, the main provisions of strategy and tactics are analyzed and justified, as well as the most effective options for performing techniques. athletes practice in the detailed development and implementation of strategic and tactical plans in relation to performances in individual matches, tournament competitions, and competition cycles. Studying the technique, strategy and tactics of the main rivals, various aspects of their preparedness, simulate their game and develop their own

countermodels.

The improvement of strategy, tactics and techniques is aimed at ensuring comprehensive readiness for fierce, acute and long-term competitions in diverse but specific competitive conditions.

Therefore, from time to time it is important to bring the training conditions as close as possible to the conditions of official competitions, to create an environment that requires the manifestation of qualities, as during competitions. Students acquire the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities simultaneously with the development of strategic and tactical thinking, strong-willed qualities, and the ability to clearly control their behavior in competitions. When improving strategy and tactics, tennis players are tasked with achieving maximum purposefulness, consistency and flexibility in their actions. Special attention should be paid to the formation of the ability to act in accordance with strategic and tactical tasks, achieving unity in their implementation.

Improving the technique involves "polishing" movements, expanding their variability, and achieving high performance of each technique in a competitive game. To improve the technique, various technical means and special devices continue to be widely used, and especially those that allow you to improve percussion movements and develop physical qualities in relation to them, create conditions for repeated repetition of strokes in difficult playing conditions at a rapid pace.

In training, exercises are used at the walls, around the table with the direction of conditional and non-conditional strikes, training ball games and competitive games.

Exercises on the training walls. They play an important role in the training of table tennis players and are mainly aimed at improving technique. However, some tactical combinations are also mastered on the training wall (albeit in simplified conditions). With goals, it is recommended to train not only on a regular training wall, but also on a universal wall, where the ball flies in an unexpected direction for the player.

The exercises are performed around the table in the direction of predetermined strokes. In such exercises, the athlete knows in advance the direction of the partner's blows, so he has the opportunity to focus all his attention on his movements. They are especially useful when it is necessary to correct deficiencies in technique, to try tactical combinations. During a normal game, it is very difficult to significantly change the movements. Therefore, in the absence of an unexpected factor, it is justified to correct technical shortcomings in somewhat simplified conditions. With these exercises, you should regularly improve flat strokes and various ball rotations, strikes at all three points, different strength, direction and shape of the ball's flight path, as well as different tactical direction.

In the game, technique is largely subordinated to tactics, so the movements during strikes vary depending on their tactical orientation. So, in most cases, the movements during the preparatory kick to reach the net are somewhat different from the usual punches from the back line. In this regard, it is necessary to improve the technique not only in its pure form, but also in relation to various options for solving tactical tasks. It is necessary to constantly improve the main groups of rebound strikes, which differ in different tactical orientation:

- combined "leading" attacks (a series of strikes with which they prepare the conditions for a circular strike or a net);

- the final attacking strikes;
- preparatory attacking strokes for reaching the net (with which the exit to the net is carried out);
- circumventing counterattacking attacks.

Exercises with a predetermined direction of strikes allow you to "grind" movements in relation to serves of various tactical orientation.

Exercises around the table in the direction of air ball strikes. The exercises of this group are distinguished primarily by the presence of a surprise factor in the partner's actions. The student strives to prepare and carry out the planned strikes and tactical combinations. The conditions for performing these exercises are close to the conditions of a competitive game. The exercises are dominated by intense gaming activities. Exercises with threesomes are particularly beneficial: they make it possible to act at a fast pace (it is especially important that when using these exercises, those involved have a large number of balls at their disposal).

Educational and competitive games with score. Games with a score are divided into educational and competitive:

- training games are conducted with certain conventions, special strategic and tactical tasks;
- competitive games bring the competition conditions as close as possible and aim players to win.

To consolidate individual strikes and tactical combinations, to try out various types, methods and forms of action, to gain experience in countering various variants of tactics of a conditional opponent – this is the main task of educational games with a score. In this kind of games, individual tasks are also given, aimed at the preferential use of certain strokes in order to improve them, eliminate errors. So, if one of the students does not succeed in a backhand at a high point, then his partner can be given the following task: when going to the net, perform mainly long, strong-twisted punches with a high bounce of the ball under a backhand to the defender.

In training games, various strategy and tactics options are tested, taking into account the model characteristics of the most likely competitors in the competition. In such cases, one of the trainees is assigned to simulate the opponent's game, and the other is to try out various options for strategy and tactics, to find the most effective ones that correspond to the individual characteristics of the game.

In educational games, students practice developing and implementing a variety of strategic and tactical plans.

Scoring training games should not be considered as mandatory precursors to competitive games. Both types of games should complement each other, be used in optimal combinations and be regarded as dress rehearsals before performances in official competitions.

Educational and competitive games allow you to try out various options for competitive behavior, develop such important psychological qualities as observation and the ability to predict the intentions and actions of rivals. These qualities are expressed in the ability to unravel their strategic and tactical plans, plans during the preparation of individual strikes, to identify the features of their physical and mental state in the smallest details of actions, gestures, poses, and appearance of rivals.

An integral part of strategic and tactical training is detailed analysis, together with athletes, of the progress and results of training and competitive games, as well as meetings in official competitions. To analyze the effectiveness of various actions, identify the causes of victories and defeats, and compare the characteristics of actions in various matches, it is very important to have objective data characterizing the different sides of each tennis player's games. Special game records are kept to collect such data.

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